

Vincent Van Gogh's "The Room in Arles" and France's Spoliation of the Matsukata Collection

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For many years, especially during the colonial period or during various armed conflicts, thousands of works of art have been literally looted.

This is the case of the painting "*The Room in Arles*" by Vincent Van Gogh from the Matsukata collection.

Japanese industrialist and important art collector, Kōjirō Matsukata was born on January 17, 1866. The son of a former Prime Minister of Japan, he was trained in Western culture after studying in the United States, graduating from Yale University.

During two long stays in Europe, in London and Paris between 1916 and 1922, he built up an impressive collection of modern art of several thousand paintings, ranging from Claude Monet to Pablo Picasso, from Paul Gauguin to Gustave Courbet, including Vincent Van Gogh, Paul Cézanne, Paul-Auguste Renoir and Kees Van Dongen.

Endowed with a very sure taste, Kōjirō Matsukata acquired "*The Room in Arles*" in the early 1920s from the famous Parisian dealer Paul Rosenberg, on the advice of Yukiō Yashirō, an art historian to whom he had entrusted the mission of assisting him in the constitution of his collection.

On the theme of his room, Van Gogh produced three almost identical paintings. The first, exhibited at the Van Gogh Museum in Amsterdam, was painted in October 1888 and damaged during a flood during the painter's hospitalization in the city of Arles. The following year, the latter made two copies: the first copy,

of the same dimensions, is now kept at the Art Institute of Chicago; the second copy, the one acquired by Matsukata, is smaller in size. It is an oil on canvas measuring 57.3 cm by 73.5 cm.

Kōjirō Matsukata plans to create a museum in Japan that will bring together the works of the greatest Western masters. But the repatriation of works to the empire of the rising sun comes up against Japanese tax legislation which applies 100% customs duties. Faced with this taxation, he decided to store part of his immense collection in London, at the "*Pantehnicon*" storage room, and in Paris, where his friend Léonce Bénédicté agreed to temporarily store the works in the cellars of the Musée Rodin.

Kōjirō Matsukata was unlucky. On October 9, 1939, a violent fire broke out in the London storage room and almost the entire collection was destroyed by fire¹

It was his trusted man, Kōsaborō Hiōki, who watched over the rest of the works stored in Paris.

In 1940, Hiōki decided to protect most of the Parisian collection from the German threat. He transported the 336 paintings to the property owned by his partner in Abondant in the Eure-et-Loir department. The sculptures, 58 in number, which are more difficult to transport, remain at the Musée Rodin.

A precautionary seizure without legal basis

But at the end of the war, fate seemed to be relentless on the collection since an ordinance of the provisional government of the French Republic dated October 5, 1944 placed the "*enemy property*" under sequestration, Japan being a member of the Rome-Berlin-Tokyo tripartite pact opposed to the Allies². At this stage, it is a purely precautionary measure. The management of the estates took charge of the sequestered works and, in September 1945, gave its agreement to transfer the twenty-five

¹ Newspaper "*Le Nouvelliste Valaisan*", edition of 10 October 1939, p. 2

² Ordinance of 5 October 1944 on the declaration and sequestration of property belonging to enemies. Official Journal of the French Republic of 7 October 1944, p.885

or so sealed boxes of paintings to the reserves of the Museum of Modern Art. The inventory drawn up on this occasion mentions several hundred works including paintings on canvas, watercolours, drawings, books, engravings and bronzes. In September 1948, Bernard Dorival, curator of the Museum of Modern Art, wrote the following note to Alain Poher, Secretary of State for the Budget³:

"NOTE ON THE MATSUKATA COLLECTION

As a result of the war between France and Japan, the collection of works of art that he had assembled was sequestered in the collection of Mr. Matsukata, a Japanese subject, who had lived in Japan since 1925 and who had left in France, in the care of his representative and compatriot, Mr. Hiōki. This collection, one of the most beautiful in France, is almost unique in the world. Among the eleven hundred or so books that make up the Collection, we should mention:

- about fifty sculptures by Rodin, both in bronze and marble, which constitute an unrivalled ensemble in the universe, except for the Rodin Museum*
- a dozen sculptures by Bourpelle*
- eight paintings by Courbet, including the famous "Flagey Peasants returning from the Fair"*
- Billet's famous painting, "Daphnis and Chloe"*
- one of Manet's most beautiful paintings, "The Bock Waitress"*
- a large set of twenty-five paintings by Claude Monet*
- three works painted by Pissaro*
- the illustrious "Portrait of Berthe the Deaf" by Toulouse-Lautrec*
- Renoir's masterpiece, "Parisian women dressed as Algerians" as well as a portrait and a landscape by the same artist*
- six watercolours by Cézanne*
- a unique collection of eight paintings by Gauguin, including the prestigious "Vairumati"*
- one of Van Gogh's major pieces, "The Artist's Room in Arles"*

³ Bernard Dorival, *"Note on the Matsukata Collection"*, September 1948, AN, 20150044/120. See also Maxime Georges Métraux and Léa Saint-Raymond, *"Van Gogh's Room in Arles, The Centerpiece of the Matsukata*

- an important set of paintings by Maurice Denis*
- an important set of paintings by Marquet*
- three works by Picasso, including the "Great Reader in Grey"*
- two paintings by Soutine*
- not to mention drawings by Delacroix, Puvis de Chavannes, Rodin, paintings by Bonvin, Lépine, etc.*

The acquisition of this collection by the National Museums represents for them their last chance to fill gaps that can never be filled again. When we know their paucity of masterpieces by Renoir, Toulouse Lautrec, Gauguin, Van Gogh, we measure the importance they can attach to the entry of this collection into the national artistic collections. This entry should be done in two stages

- 1 - confiscation of the collection as reparation for war damage caused by Japan;*
- 2 - Allocation of the confiscated collection to the National Museums. In this regard, it would be essential that the Administration of the Estates did not put it up for sale, as the prices that its masterpieces would reach in a public sale did not allow us to hope that the National Museums would be able to acquire them."*

The Matsukata collection, which has been sequestered, is used to contribute to the cultural influence of France abroad. Travelling exhibitions are organised in Brussels, Stuttgart, Vienna, London, Basel, Copenhagen, Amsterdam, Zurich, Rome, Florence, Moscow, Warsaw, but also in New York and San Francisco.

Kōjirō Matsukata died on June 24, 1950 at the age of 84.

His son, Kōsuke Matsukata and son-in-law, Shigeharu Matsumotō, are now in charge of the collection.

Georges Salles, director of the Museums of France and also director of the Louvre Museum, asked Jacques Chazelle, secretary of the French Mission in Japan, to contact Matsukata's heirs in

Sequestration", Noto Revue culturelle, June 2020, pp.94-121.

See also Yuichirō Miyashita, *"The Cultural Presence of France in Japan and the Matsukata Collection"*, International Relations, 2008/2 (134), pp.37-53

order to find common ground so that France could preserve some of the works placed under sequestration. Indeed, the French authorities are well aware that the precautionary seizure of the collection carried out at the Liberation is based on an uncertain and questionable legal basis. Article 2 of the Ordinance of 5 October 1944 issued by General de Gaulle considers that "*all nationals of enemy States, regardless of their place of residence or habitual residence, are deemed to be enemies for the purposes of this Ordinance. Bulgaria, Finland, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Japan, Romania, Thailand and the United States shall be considered enemies for the purposes of this Ordinance.*"

However, for Japan to have been legally considered an "*enemy*" (and therefore for the goods in the Matsukata collection to have been legally sequestered), France would still have had to have been in a state of war with Japan. However, since the French Revolution, there has been an intangible principle according to which only Parliament can authorize the declaration of war.

In addition, Article 1 of the Third Hague Convention of 18 October 1907 on the Opening of Hostilities stipulates that *the "Contracting Powers recognize that hostilities between them shall not commence without a prior and unequivocal warning, which shall take the form of either a reasoned declaration of war or an ultimatum with a conditional declaration of war"*.

This essential formality was respected by France and England in September 1939 in the state of war following the ultimatum addressed to Germany to stop the invasion of Poland. But as far as Japan is concerned, France has never formally declared war or issued an ultimatum with a conditional declaration of war. And this was all the more so since during the period of the Vichy government, France was neutral vis-à-vis Japan, an ally of Germany and Italy.

Following the appeal of 18 June 1940, when the French state regime was being set up, General de Gaulle, by installing Free France in London,

began a journey that would bring him back to Paris, four years later as head of the Government of the Republic. There are five steps:

- 28 June 1940, London, the British government recognises General de Gaulle as leader of the Free French
- 27 October 1940, Brazzaville, creation of the Council for the Defence of the Empire;
- 24 September 1941, London, creation of the French National Committee;
- 3 June 1943, Algiers, creation of the French Committee for National Liberation;
- 3 June 1944, Algiers, creation of the Provisional Government of the French Republic.

When Japan attacked the Pearl Harbour base on December 7, 1941, General de Gaulle, leader of Free France, issued a simple communiqué reproduced below dated the next day, December 8, 1941⁴ and published in the "*Documents of the Information Service of Free France*":

"Free France declares war on Japan

The French National Committee met on 8 December under the chairmanship of General de Gaulle. He decided that a state of war existed between all the territories and all the land, sea and air forces of France and Japan.

Rear-Admiral Thierry d'Argenlieu, National Commissioner Delegate in the Pacific, who has recently been invested with the dual mission of ensuring the defence of all the territories under the authority of the National Committee in the Pacific: New Caledonia, Tahiti, the French Establishments in Oceania, the Condominium of the New Hebrides, and of representing France in the Far East, has been instructed to contribute to the inter-allied effort by all the means in which he is responsible. to this end shall be in close liaison with the Authorities of Great Britain and her Dominions, the United States, and the Netherlands East Indies.

The National Committee also appeals to the entire civilian and military population of Indochina and

⁴ "*Documents du Service d'Information de la France Libre*", 15 December 1941 p.31

invites them to resist Japanese aggression by all means in their power. The National Committee, in taking these decisions, is certain to act in the name of France as a whole."

During the period of the French National Committee, Free France had a Journal officiel in which it regularly published the acts and decisions taken.

However, the declaration of war on Japan by the French National Committee was never published in the Official Journal of Free France or even notified to the Japanese authorities. It follows that the above-mentioned communiqué of 8 December 1941 has no legal character.

In addition, Article 6 of the Ordinance of 9 August 1944 on the re-establishment of republican legality on continental territory provides that⁵:

"The texts published in the Official Journal of Free France, in the Official Journal of Fighting France, in the Official Journal of the French Civil and Military Commander-in-Chief since 18 March 1943, and finally in the Official Journal of the French Republic between 10 June 1943 and the date of the promulgation of this Ordinance shall not be applicable on the continental territory of France until the date which shall be expressly fixed for each of them. »

As the communiqué declaring war on Japan of 8 December 1941 was not published in the Official Journal of Free France, it could not, of course, be the subject of an effective date of application within the meaning of Article 6 of the above-mentioned Ordinance of 9 August 1944.

Therefore, the ordinance of 5 October 1944, insofar as it provided for the sequestration of property belonging to Japanese citizens as nationals of an "enemy power", lacked a legal basis insofar as neither the Vichy regime of Marshal Pétain nor the Free France of General

de Gaulle had ever made a valid declaration of war under international law.

On October 5, 1944, Japan was therefore not in a state of war with France. Its nationals did not belong to an "enemy power".

When the Vichy regime collapsed, the Provisional Government of the French Republic asked Admiral Decoux, the governor general of Indochina appointed by Marshal Pétain, not to resign from his post and to continue to "collaborate" with the Japanese who occupied the territory⁶. But at the time of the fall of Manila (March 5, 1945), the Tokyo government unilaterally put an end to this hitherto peaceful collaboration. Unable to tolerate the presence of a foreign force in the midst of their system that threatened to become hostile, the Japanese summoned, on March 9, 1945, Admiral Decoux in Saigon and General Aymé in Hanoi to submit to them and place the French forces under their control, until they were disarmed. The governor-general and the French superior commander refused to comply with the summons, and the Japanese army attacked the French garrisons.

The Japanese aggression of March 9, 1945, resulted in the France, and only from that date, being indisputably a belligerent in the Pacific War. This analysis is confirmed in these terms by General de Gaulle himself in his third volume of the "War Memoirs"⁷:

"I was happy to envisage that we would come to blows in Indochina... knowing the malice of the allies, especially the Americans, with regard to our position in the Far East, I considered it essential that the conflict should not end there without us having become belligerents there too."

If France had "become" belligerent as a result of this aggression, this meant that it had not been so before, the simple unofficial declaration of intent of December 8, 1941 by the French National Committee being in this respect obviously insufficient to characterize the

⁵ Ordinance of 9 August 1944 on the re-establishment of republican legality on continental territory. Official Journal of the French Republic of 10 August 1944 p.688

⁶ Lazar Focsaneanu. "The Peace Treaties of Japan". In: *Annuaire français de droit international*, volume 6, 1960. pp. 256-290

⁷ Charles de Gaulle, "Mémoires de guerre", III, Paris, Pion, 1960, pp. 163-164

effective state of war between France and Japan, which General de Gaulle implicitly admitted.

In these circumstances, the sequestration of the Matsukata collection is vitiated, for this first reason, by manifest irregularity.

A peace treaty inapplicable to the Matsukata collection

Because of this fragile legal foundation, the French authorities will continue to obtain an amicable settlement in order to preserve the collection. France is well aware that it is urgent to act before the peace treaty with Japan, which is currently being negotiated and involves all the belligerents, including the United States, is signed. Indeed, the peace treaty, the content of which the French government did not yet know, could be favourable to Japan. France fears that it will be forced to return the collection to the Matsukata family. As the collection is considered to be a private property, the French authorities believe that there is a serious risk of having to return it to the legitimate owners.

Georges Salles organised a meeting on 24 July 1950 attended by representatives of the Domaines and representatives of the Ministries of Cultural Affairs and Foreign Affairs. The minutes of this meeting concluded that it was necessary to reach an amicable agreement with the Matsukata family. If the heirs "*donate fifteen to twenty essential pieces to the national museums*", France will lift its sequestration and allow the exit from the territory "*for the rest of the collection which would constitute in Japan the museum of contemporary French art desired by Kōjirō Matsukata*".⁸

Shigeharu Matsumotō, Matsukata's son-in-law and the main interlocutor in the negotiations with the French authorities, was not in favour of this proposal and intended to recover the entire collection. It is out of the question for him to agree to any amicable agreement. But the

Japanese government is also involved in the case. Japan wants to regain an important place in the concert of nations at all costs. In the political field, it wants to be admitted to the United Nations and, in the economic field, it wants to join the GATT as a full partner. The Japanese authorities are therefore in favour of an amicable settlement, unlike the Matsukata family.

It was in this context that the San Francisco Peace Treaty⁹ was signed on September 8, 1951. France has weighed heavily in the negotiations. Article 14.2.1 of the Treaty provides that:

"Each of the Allied Powers shall have the right to seize, retain, liquidate or otherwise use all property, rights and interests

(a) Japan and Japanese nationals

(b) persons acting in place of or on behalf of Japan or Japanese nationals, and

(c) organizations owned or controlled by Japan or its nationals,

which, at the time of the initial entry into force of the present Treaty, were under the jurisdiction of the said Allied Power. The property, rights and interests referred to in this sub-paragraph shall include the property, rights and interests now blocked by, or vested in, the authorities of the Allied Powers entrusted with the management of enemy property, or in the possession or control of such authorities, and which belonged to any of the natural persons or bodies referred to in (a), (b) or (c) above, or were held or administered on their behalf at the time such assets came under the control of such authorities.

The right provided for in subparagraph (l) above to seize, retain, liquidate, or otherwise dispose of such property, shall be exercised in accordance with the law of the Allied Power concerned, and the owner thereof shall have only such rights as are granted by such law. »

Now, the French government has a legal basis to preserve the collection based on the provisions of Article 14.2.1 of the San Francisco Peace Treaty.

⁸ Minutes of the meeting of Monday, July 24, 1950 at the Directorate-General for Arts and Letters, AN,20150044/120.

⁹ United Nations Treaty Series – 1952. pp 47-164

Except that the treaty only concerned "*enemy property*" and that Japan had never been officially in a state of war with France, the above-mentioned ordinance of 5 October 1944 signed by General de Gaulle contenting itself, in a highly questionable legal manner, with "*deeming an enemy*" of Japan under very hazardous conditions.

In negotiations with both the Matsukata family and the Japanese government, the French government did not fail to highlight the provisions of the Treaty of San Francisco to affirm that France could perfectly well preserve the entire collection.

A partial donation based on an irregular legislative procedure

Strengthened by its position (but aware of its weakness from a legal point of view), France nevertheless proposed to keep about twenty works (the most important) and to "*donate*" the rest of the collection to Japan, on the condition that these works be exhibited in a museum specially built for this purpose. It was agreed, however, that the "*donation*" of the rest of the collection would be made exclusively to the Japanese state and that the Matsukata family would have to renounce all its rights.

This proposal was finally accepted, reluctantly, by the Japanese side. The plans for a "*Museum of Western Art, Matsukata Collection of French Art*" in Tokyo were entrusted to the Franco-Swiss architect Le Corbusier, flanked by three Japanese architects, Sakakura Junzō, Maekawa and Yōshizaka Takamasa.

The French authorities set in motion the legislative procedure to make the "*donation*". Indeed, the principle of the inalienability of public collections necessarily implies that a law be passed to validate the operation. On 7 March 1958, a bill was passed by the National

Assembly. The file is then sent to the Senate. But following the Algerian crisis, the President of the Republic, René Coty, called on General de Gaulle and entrusted him with the task of a new government. A new Constitution was drawn up. The bill before the Senate is suspended. On 3 June 1958, a so-called "*full powers*" law was passed. This law provides that "*for a period of six months from the promulgation of this law, the Government of the Republic invested on 1 June 1958 shall adopt by decrees, known as ordinances, the measures deemed necessary for the recovery of the nation, which may, in particular, repeal, modify or replace the legislative provisions in force. These decrees may not relate to matters reserved to the law by the republican constitutional tradition resulting in particular from the preamble to the Constitution of 1946 and the Declaration of the Rights of Man of 1789, nor to the exercise of public and trade union freedoms, nor to the qualification of crimes and offences, and the determination of the penalties applicable to them. criminal procedure, nor on the adjustment of the fundamental guarantees granted to citizens, nor on electoral legislation. They will be adopted by the Council of Ministers, after the opinion of the Council of State*".¹⁰

In addition, article 92 of the new Constitution provides that "*the legislative measures necessary for the establishment of institutions and, until such establishment, for the functioning of the public authorities shall be taken by the Council of Ministers, after consulting the Council of State, by ordinance having the force of law. During the period provided for in paragraph 1 of Article 91 [4 months], the Government is authorized to lay down by ordinances having the force of law and adopted in the same form the electoral regime of the assemblies provided for by the Constitution. During the same period and under the same conditions, the Government may also take the measures it deems necessary for the life of the nation, the protection of citizens or the safeguarding of freedoms in all matters.*"

¹⁰ Ln°58-520 of 3 June 1958 relating to full powers.

Official Journal of the French Republic of 4 June 1958, p. 5327. Official Journal of the French Republic of 4 June 1958, p. 5327

Basing itself, in an extremely questionable manner in law, on the aforementioned Article 92 of the Constitution alone, the Government, which wanted to move quickly and which did not wish this matter to go through the traditional legislative procedure, issued an order dated 17 December 1958 authorizing the transfer to the Japanese State of the major part of the Matsukata Collection. except for eighteen works that he intends to keep for himself¹¹.

However, this ordinance does not fall within the restrictive scope provided for in Article 92 of the Constitution.

It is difficult to see how the transfer of the Matsukata collection to the Japanese state would be insignificant, directly or indirectly, as a matter of "legislative measures necessary for the establishment of institutions".

For the sake of completeness, it will be observed that such a transfer does not fall within the scope of the Full Powers Act of 3 June 1958, which is not covered by the Ordinance of 17 December 1958.

Indeed, the transfer in question is clearly not "necessary for the recovery of the nation".

In reality, the French Government deliberately evaded the normal legislative procedure through Parliament in order to illegally accelerate a derogatory transfer under ordinary law that evades the law in favour of an ordinance that is totally arbitrary and devoid of any legal basis.

We are in the presence of a second manifest irregularity.

Works preserved by France

The order refers to and refers to several exchanges of letters that took place between the French and Japanese authorities.

First of all, there is a letter from the Japanese Minister of Foreign Affairs (the Gaimushō) dated October 4, 1955 addressed to the France Ambassador to Japan in which¹²:

"(1) The Government of Japan confirms its decision to construct a new museum on the former grounds of Ryouin-in Temple in Tokyo's Uenō Park, to house and display the artworks collected by the late Mr. Matsukata. The Japanese Government has already begun preliminary work on the construction of this museum;

2) He intends to give this museum the name of "National Museum of Western Art", and the subtitle "Matsukata Collection of French Art";

3) The Government of Japan confirms that the donation of the collection is made to the Government of Japan by the Government of France and not to the Matsukata family, and that it has taken all necessary measures to prevent any possible claims by anyone on the collection. It will forever remain the national property of Japan, as soon as the donation is made.

On this point, the Japanese Government deems it necessary to announce that the heirs of the late Mr. Matsukata, as well as of the late Mr. Hiōki, administrator of the collection in Paris, have officially confirmed to it by respective letters, a copy of which is attached, dated April 1, 1955 and September 30, 1954, that they have renounced all rights of claim and privileges over the said collection."

Secondly, there is a letter dated 1 April 1955, signed by Saburō Matsukata (in his capacity as heir) in which¹³:

"I, the undersigned, Saburō Matsukata, declare that I renounce my rights to the Matsukata Collection, which has become the property of the French Government according to the clauses of the Peace Treaty of San Francisco of 1951, in the event that, thanks to the benevolence of the French Government, the said collection is handed

¹¹ Ordinance No. 58-1246 of December 17, 1958 authorizing the transfer of ownership of works of art to the Japanese State. Official Journal of the French Republic of 19 December 1958, p. 11422

¹² Official Journal of the French Republic of 19 December 1958, p.11423

¹³ Ibid, p. 11423

over to Japan, and have no objection to the fact that it becomes forever the property of the Japanese Government and serves the good of culture."

The Ordinance includes in an appendix the list of works from the transferred collection¹⁴.

This list includes several hundred paintings, drawings, watercolours, engravings, books and sculptures. In particular, there are works by Picasso, Monet, Renoir, Rodin, Delacroix, Pissaro, Courbet, Van Dongen, Cézanne, Corot...

But this list does not include the entire collection. Indeed, France has reserved the lion's share by keeping eighteen of the most beautiful pieces.

These are the following works:

N°1 – *"The Artist's Room in Arles"* by Vincent Van Gogh – Currently at the Musée d'Orsay in Paris under inventory number RF 1959 2

N°2 – *"Justine Dieulh, known as Berthe the Deaf in the Garden"* by Henri de Toulouse-Lautrec – Currently at the Musée d'Orsay in Paris under inventory number RF 1959 3

N°3 – *"The Hanging Poultry"* by Chaïm Soutine – Currently at the Georges Pompidou National Centre for Art and Culture in Paris under inventory number AM 3612 P

N°4 – *"The Bellboy"* by Chaïm Soutine - Currently at the Georges Pompidou National Centre for Art and Culture in Paris under inventory number AM 3611 P

N°5 – *"The Bourgeois of Calais"* by Auguste Rodin – Currently at the Musée Rodin in Paris under the inventory number S.00450

N°6 – *"The Grey Reader"* by Pablo Picasso - Currently at the Georges Pompidou National Centre for Art and Culture in Paris under inventory number AM 3613 P

N°7 – *"Giotto"* by Gustave Moreau - Currently at the Musée d'Orsay in Paris under inventory number RF 31174

N°8 – *"The Saint-Michel Bridge"* by Albert Marquet - Currently at the Georges Pompidou

National Centre for Art and Culture in Paris under the inventory number AM 3614 P

N°9 – *"The Bock Waitress"* by Edouard Manet - Currently at the Musée d'Orsay in Paris under inventory number RF 1959 4

N°10 – *"Vairumati"* by Paul Gauguin - Currently at the Musée d'Orsay in Paris under inventory number RF 1959 5

N°11 – *"Mill in Brittany"* by Paul Gauguin - Currently at the Musée d'Orsay in Paris under inventory number RF 1959 6

N°12 – *"The Schuffenecker Family"* by Paul Gauguin Currently at the Musée d'Orsay in Paris under the inventory number RF 1959 8

N°13 – *"Still Life"* by Paul Gauguin - Currently at the Musée d'Orsay in Paris under inventory number RF 1959 7

N°14 – *"The Peasants of Flagey Returning from the Fair"* by Gustave Courbet Currently at the Musée d'Orsay in Paris under the inventory number RF 1959 9

N°15 – *"Study after Giorgione"* by Paul Cézanne – Currently in the Louvre Museum in Paris under inventory number RF 31173

N°16 – *"The table known as jars and jam jars"* by Paul Cézanne Currently at the Musée d'Orsay in Paris under the inventory number RF 31172

N°17 – *"La montagne Sainte-Victoire"* by Paul Cézanne - Currently at the Musée d'Orsay in Paris under inventory number RF 31171

N°18 – *"Decoration of the dining room - Still Life with Brie, Still Life with Hare, Still Life with Duck"* Three friezes by François Bonvin - Currently at the Musée d'Orsay in Paris under the inventory numbers RF 1959 10, RF 1959 11, RF 1959 12

"The room in Arles" is the centerpiece of the collection. The one that has the most artistic value. The one whose price is priceless.

It was made in 1889, when Van Gogh was interned in the psychiatric hospital of Saint-Rémy-de-Provence. The painting is all the more unique because the artist painted it especially as a gift to his mother.

¹⁴ Ibid pp. 11424-11427

The whole painting is based on the work of the pictorial material which is both color and texture. It is textured, because Van Gogh manipulates it almost like a sculptor, he plays with the shape of the brushstroke, he accentuates the reliefs by creating impasto, on the pillows for example. Everywhere he leaves visible the trace of the knife, brush or brush he used to apply the paste to the canvas.

In a letter to his brother Theo, Van Gogh described the painting in these terms: *"The walls are a pale purple. The floor is red checkered. The wood of the bed and the chairs are a fresh buttery yellow. The very light lime sheet and pillows, the scarlet red blanket..."*¹⁵

Violation of the Rights of Matsukata's Heirs

This whole affair is a shameless spoliation of the rights of Matsukata's heirs.

Indeed, it appears very clearly:

-that in the absence of official belligerence between France and Japan, the Matsukata collection could not be seized, pursuant to the order of 5 October 1944, as belonging to a national of an *"enemy power"*

-that in the absence of official belligerence between France and Japan, Article 14.2.1 of the San Francisco Peace Treaty of 8 September 1951 did not apply to Japanese nationals

-that it is therefore in a totally illegal manner that France has preserved eighteen works forming part of the collection by abusively invoking the provisions of the aforementioned treaty

-that, with regard to the rest of the collection, it was in a totally unconstitutional manner that France used the ordinance procedure to validate a *"donation"* to Japan, such a donation, assuming it to be legal, which is not the case, falling under the law and therefore under Parliament alone

The heirs' relinquishment of their rights to the Matsukata collection

The French authorities have ensured that the heirs of the Matsukata collection expressly waive all their rights. The renunciation expressed in the letter of April 1, 1955, signed by Saburō Matsukata (see above) is not, however, general and absolute. Indeed, this letter expressly refers to the collection insofar as *"it has become the property of the French Government according to the clauses of the Peace Treaty of San Francisco"* and insofar as *"the said collection would be handed over to Japan"* with a view to *"it becoming forever the property of the Japanese Government and serving the good of culture"*.

In the present case, however, the collection never became the property of the French Government, since the Treaty of San Francisco did not apply in the absence of proven belligerence between the two countries at the date of the precautionary seizure carried out following the order of 5 October 1944.

Moreover, since the collection was handed over to Japan according to an irregular procedure by means of an ordinance, whereas a law passed by the French Parliament was mandatory, the condition set by the renunciation is not met, since only a legally valid return can bind the heirs.

Last but not least, supposing, as a textbook hypothesis, that the *"donation"* validated by a simple ordinance is valid, the fact remains that the letter of renunciation expressly concerns only *"the collection handed over to Japan"*.

However, there are still eighteen works that France has kept in front of it, which have not been handed over to Japan and for which the heirs have not renounced their rights.

It necessarily follows that, at the very least, the heirs of the Matsukata collection retain their rights to these eighteen works of which they have been illegally despoiled.

¹⁵ Vincent Van Gogh *"Letters to his brother Theo"* - Collection l'Imaginaire, Gallimard n° 206, 1988

The rights of the heirs to claim the restitution of the eighteen works illegally preserved by France

It is clear that the eighteen works preserved by France were the subject of an appropriation tainted by a marked excess of power. A deed obtained by fraud does not create rights (CE 29 November 2002, req. 223027). This is the application of the adage "*Fraus omnia corrumpit*".

In its famous Assembly decision of 31 May 1957 (req. n°26188), the French Council of State ruled that "*administrative acts affected by a particularly serious and flagrant illegality must be regarded as non-existent and are considered null and void*".

The non-existent act is so intolerable that the judge only notes it. If the judge annulled it, it would assume that the act was at one time presumed to be legal.

It has virtually never seen the light of day.

The qualification of a non-existent act does not meet very precise criteria. Indeed, the French administrative judge uses a rather general formula which is as follows:

"An act can only be considered non-existent if it is devoid of material existence or if it is vitiated by a defect of such gravity that it affects not only its legality, but its very existence" (for example: CE, 28 Sept. 2016, req. n° 399173, ANTICOR).

A non-existent act produces two sets of effects: it can be nullified at any time and it produces no legal effect. When an act which is in fact non-existent comes before the French administrative judge, the latter must raise it of its own motion as a means of public policy (for example: CE, 5 May 1971, application no. 75655, Prefect of Paris).

The non-existent act does not create any acquired right. In other words, it is not possible to raise anything on the basis of such an act. The finding or withdrawal of a non-existent act leads to the disappearance of subsequent acts, i.e. those that were taken on the basis of it.

¹⁶ Council of State 23 November 2022, 10th chamber, req. No. 463108, International Restitutions

In the present case, the appropriation of the eighteen works constitutes an act of particularly serious illegality.

Therefore, the incorporation of these works into the public domain is non-existent. In law, such incorporation is legally non-existent and null and void, as Articles L451-3 and L451-5 of the Heritage Code and Article L3111-1 of the General Code of the Property of Public Persons, which enshrine the imprescriptibility and inalienability of public collections, being unenforceable in the event of non-existence. In addition, Article D451-19 of the Heritage Code provides that the removal of an item from an inventory of the museums of France may take place "*in the event of undue registration on the inventory*".

France's Restitution of Van Gogh's "Room at Arles" and Other Illegally Preserved Works

The chances for the heirs of the Matsukata collection to obtain, before the French Council of State, the removal from the inventory of illegally looted works with a view to their restitution are extremely low, given its consistent restrictive case law ¹⁶ ¹⁷ on the inalienability of property belonging to a public collection.

If the heirs of the Matsukata collection want to recover all or part of the collection of which they have been robbed, the only appropriate remedy is that of international justice.

In this respect, the possible referral to the European Court of Human Rights does not appear to be relevant. Indeed, this court receives several thousand applications each year. By its Protocol No. 14, which entered into force on 1 June 2010, the Court modified its procedure to deal with the increase in the number of applications submitted to it by now requiring that the damage be "*significant*". More than 95% of applications are declared inadmissible after a simple very summary examination by a single judge. In practice, a

¹⁷ Council of State 14 May 2024, 10th chamber, req. No. 491862, International Restitutions

team of lawyers assisting the single judge only selects cases that appear to merit the transfer of the file to a panel of three judges or to a chamber of the Court. The other applications are systematically rejected¹⁸.

In the present case, the most judicious remedy seems to be a complaint to the United Nations Human Rights Council for arbitrary deprivation of the right to property enshrined in Article 17 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights of 10 December 1948.

The NGO International Restitutions¹⁹, whose corporate purpose is to ensure the lawfulness of the composition of the collections of public museums, has initiated a complaint procedure with the United Nations Human Rights Council against France on behalf of the heirs of the Matsukata collection for the management of affairs as provided for in the provisions of Article 1301 of the French Civil Code.²⁰

¹⁸ In the International Restitutions v. France case concerning the controversial appropriation of the painting "The Mona Lisa" by King Francis 1st (see Article <https://www.academia.edu/120400972>), the European Court of Human Rights, ruling by a single judge, declared the application inadmissible without ruling on the merits by decision no. 14691/24 of 12 September 2024

¹⁹ www.international-restitutions.org

²⁰ Business management is defined in Article 1301 of the French Civil Code as *"a person who, without being required to do so, knowingly and usefully manages the business of another; without the knowledge or opposition of the owner of this business"*. In other words, it is a question of a person, who is called the business

manager, intervening spontaneously in the affairs of others, the owner of the business or the managed.

The particularity of business management is that it assumes that a person has acted on behalf of a third party and in his or her interest, without having been mandated by the third party, or that he or she has been kept informed. In a judgment of 21 December 1981 (Civil Chamber 1, 80-15.854), the French Court of Cassation held that a person who is not a representative may represent a third party in legal proceedings by acting as a business manager. In support of its decision, it specifies that *"no legal provision makes the validity of the action brought by the business manager subject to the acceptance of the proceedings by the third party against whom this action is brought"*